

Assessment of Nutritional Status Among Elderly Population in a Rural Area of a Teaching Hospital in Trichy

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ABSTRACT

Background: Ageing is a biological process resulting from a variety of molecular changes and cellular damage over a period of time, further leading to a decline in physical, and mental capacity and increasing the risk of development of disease with ultimate death. According to the World Health Organization, the worldwide elderly population is experiencing growth in both size and proportion, they are living longer in every country. Nutrition plays an important role among the elderly population.

Objectives: To estimate the prevalence of malnutrition status among elderly population and to find out the association between malnutrition and socio-demographic status.

Methodology: A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in rural area of Trichy district. A total of 580 participants were selected by simple random sampling. Elderly population aged ≥ 60 years were screened for malnutrition status using Mini Nutrition Assessment (MNA) tool.

Results: A total of 580 participants were included in the study. Among the study participants 55.7 % were females. Majority of the study participants were aged between 60 – 70 years (55.7%). Among the study participants 11.3% were malnourished, 52.3% were at risk of malnutrition. Statistically significant association was observed between socio-economic variables, chronic diseases and Malnutrition (p value <0.05).

Conclusion: Malnutrition is an important health issue in elderly population. To prevent elderly malnutrition early intervention with a multi-dimensional approach is recommended.

Key words: Ageing, Elderly, Malnutrition, Mini-nutritional assessment, Under-nutrition.

INTRODUCTION

Ageing is a biological process resulting from a variety of molecular changes and cellular damage over a period of time, further leading to a decline in physical, and mental capacity and increasing the risk of development of disease with ultimate death. According to the World Health Organization, the worldwide elderly population is experiencing growth in both size and proportion, they are living longer in every country. At present there is a rise in the number of elderly population aged 60 years and above from 1 billion in 2020 to 1.4 billion in 2030, where it is expected to double (2.1 billion) in 2050. By 2050, two-thirds of the world's elderly

population will live in low and middle-income countries. [1]. Malnutrition is a state of being undernourished, which can be either due to nutrition excess (over-nutrition) or deficiency (under-nutrition). It is a serious health problem among the elderly population in hospitals, nursing homes and in community. Malnutrition can lead to a decrease in functional status, decreased bone mass, impaired, muscle function immune dysfunction, anaemia, reduced cognitive function, delayed surgery recovery, poor wound healing, and increased hospital readmission rates with severe morbidity and mortality [2]. Nutrition plays an important role among the elderly population.

Aging itself can cause a decrease in food intake due to loss of appetite, where their recommended nutritional requirements are not achieved leading to major risk factors for the development of chronic and degenerative diseases. Due to inadequate and improper nutrition intake, which includes both macro and micro nutrients in their diet elderly population is at risk of development of protein energy malnutrition (PEM) by nearly 23% to 60% [3]. In India, 56% of elderly population was illiterate as per the 2011 census. These vulnerable groups are economically dependent on others for their day-to-day maintenance. According to Golden Burden of Disease 2017, a total of 990,9501 deaths in India were reported. Out of these, 59% occupy elderly population. The most common diseases causing death among elderly are cardiovascular diseases, chronic respiratory diseases, cancer & stroke. The major causes of DALYs lost in India among elderly are hypertension, diabetes, respiratory illness & heart diseases. These are chronic diseases with increasing age as asymptomatic long duration of illness, deterioration of various organ system functions, common risk factors related to lifestyle with long-term follow-up and care. At the individual level, awareness about health care illness & primary care physicians of elderly is needed. Prioritization should be given on continuous education on the approach and management of common diseases like hypertension, stroke, heart disease, diabetes, and mental health. Apart from diagnostic skills to address the needs of the elderly, newer skills like behavioral counselling for addictions, psychological counselling for mental health, and palliative care with pain management at the primary level should be prioritized to address the non-communicable disease burden [4].

To assess the malnutrition status among elderly only few studies were conducted in India using MNA questionnaire. Since malnutrition can result to several adverse outcomes in future [5]. In India, the prevalence of malnutrition among the elderly was 18.29% and risk of malnutrition was 48.17% respectively. More among females (16.67%), urban areas (19.29%) and northern region (27.37%) [6]. Good nutrition helps in the prevention of acute and chronic diseases, the ability to function independently & recovery from illness among elderly population [2]. Diet alone is not enough to meet the age-specific requirements in elderly. The addition of nutritional supplements is required in prevention of chronic diseases [7]. Since elderly population is vulnerable to nutritional deficiencies, assessment and evaluation of nutritional status are major challenges for disease prevention as well as improvement in health care services. Hence this study was conducted to estimate the prevalence of malnutrition status among elderly population and to find out the association between malnutrition and socio-demographic status.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

A community-based cross-sectional study was conducted in the rural field practice area of a teaching hospital in Trichy district over a period of 5 months. The rural field practice area consists of 9 villages divided into four sectors covering a population of around 19,956.

Study population: The study was conducted among the elderly population aged ≥ 60 years.

Inclusion criteria: Elderly people aged 60 years and above residing in the rural field practice area of a teaching hospital in Trichy district who could understand, respond to questionnaires & willing to participate in the study were included.

Exclusion criteria: Participants who were severely ill, bedridden, refused to give consent & who could not be contacted even after three attempts were excluded from the study.

Sample Size: The sample size was calculated by using the formula $n = Z^2 pq / d^2$ ($Z = 1.96$, $p = 17.9\%$ (Yuvaraj et al" [8], $q = 82.1\%$, $d = 18\%$ Relative error). The final sample size was calculated to be 544. Out of 544 participants, only 530 were covered based on inclusion and exclusion criteria.

Recruitment process: Households were the primary sampling units. Probability proportional sampling (PPS) technique was used to select the desired sample from each village and simple random sampling technique was used to select the study subjects from each household in the village. After getting informed consent from the study participants, data was collected using semi-structured questionnaires.

Study tools: It consists of two parts. Part 1 includes information regarding socio-demographic profiles of the study participant and part 2 consists of Mini nutritional assessment (MNA) scale which is a validated scale with

Cronbach's alpha score of 0.71 consisting of 18 items. MNA questionnaire consists of two parts: screening and assessment. Screening part includes history of food intake in the past three months, weight loss, mobility, acute diseases, neuropsychological problems and Body Mass Index (BMI). Assessment part includes drug intake, mode of feeding, mid-arm & calf circumference, protein intake and fluid intake. This scale is widely used for screening and assessing the nutritional status of elderly during the past 3 months with a maximum score of 30 points. A score of < 17 is considered as malnourished, 17 to 23.5 considered as at risk of malnutrition and 24-30 is considered as normal nutritional status. For anthropometric assessments, height was measured using a portable stadiometer, weight was measured using portable weighing scale to the nearest 0.1 kg. Mid Upper Arm Circumference (MUAC) was measured using a non-stretchable measuring tape to the nearest 0.1 cm. Ethical clearance were obtained from the Institutional Ethical Committee (IEC No:047).

Statistical analysis

Data entry was done in Microsoft Excel. Data analysis was carried out using statistical package SPSS IBM version 26.0. Descriptive measures such as mean and standard deviation were calculated for normally distributed data. Chi-square test was used to find out the association between socio-demographic variables and malnutrition. For all statistical tests, a two-sided probability of $p < 0.05$ was considered significant.

RESULTS

A total of 530 participants were included in the study. Figure 1 shows the overall prevalence of Malnutrition was 11.3%. The sociodemographic characteristics of the study participants were described in Table I. Most of them were living in a nuclear family (62.5%). Only 8% of the participants were living alone and 46% with a spouse. Among the study participants, 51.1% were financially independent and 48.9% were financially dependent. Most participants (64.9%) were currently not working and (35.1%) were currently working. Among the study participants 75.2% were married. Majority of the study participants (57.4%) were suffering from chronic disease. Among these 30.2% were hypertensive and 21.7% were diabetic.

Table II shows association between malnutrition and socio-demographic characteristics of study individuals. Statistically significant association was observed between gender, age, chronic disease and malnutrition ($p < 0.05$). Strong association was found between socio-economic class and malnutrition ($p < 0.001$).

FIGURE 1 : PREVALENCE OF MALNUTRITION

TABLE 1: DESCRIPTIVE DATA SHOWING SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS AMONG STUDY PARTICIPANTS (n = 530)

CHARACTERISTICS	CATEGORY	FREQUENCY (%)
Gender	Male	235 (44.3%)
	female	295 (55.7%)
Age	60-70 year	295 (55.7%)
	71-80 years	196 (37.0%)
	>80 years	39 (7.4%)
Education	Illiterate	228 (43.0%)
	Primary school	187 (35.2%)
	Secondary/higher secondary school	86 (16.2%)
Financial status	Dependent	259 (48.9%)
	Independent	271 (51.1%)
Source of income	Old age pension	46 (8.7%)
	Dependent on children	249 (47.0%)
	Retirement pension	43 (8.1%)
	Currently working	186 (35.1%)
Type of family	Nuclear	331 (62.5%)
	Extended	163 (30.8%)
	Joint	36 (6.8%)
Socio-economic status	Upper middle class	163 (30.8%)
	Middle class	230 (43.4%)
	Lower class	137 (25.8%)

TABLE II: ASSOCIATION OF MALNUTRITION AND SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS OF THE PARTICIPANTS (n= 530).

SOCIO-DEMOGRAPHIC CHARACTERISTICS	MNS SCORE			P value
	NORMAL n (%) 193 (36.4%)	AT RISK n (%) 277 (52.3%)	MALNOURISHED n (%) 61 (11.3%)	
Gender				0.004
Male (235)	104 (53.9 %)	107 (38.6 %)	24 (40.0 %)	
Female (295)	89 (46.1 %)	170 (61.4 %)	36 (60.0 %)	
Age				0.001
60 – 70 yrs (295)	131 (67.9%)	136 (49.1%)	28 (46.7%)	
71 – 80 yrs (196)	52 (26.9 %)	118 (42.6 %)	26 (43.3 %)	
> 80 yrs (39)	10 (5.2 %)	23 (8.3 %)	6 (10.0 %)	
Chronic diseases (304)	102 (52.8 %)	156 (56.3 %)	46 (76.7 %)	0.004
Socio-economic class				< 0.001
Upper middle (163)	63 (38.6 %)	84 (51.5 %)	16 (9.8 %)	
Middle (230)	104 (45.2 %)	103 (44.8 %)	23 (10.0 %)	
Lower (137)	26 (19.0 %)	90 (65.7 %)	21 (15.3 %)	

DISCUSSION

In this present study, nutritional status among elderly population was assessed in rural area of Trichy district. Our study shows that malnourishment was higher among females when compared with males. Similar results were reported by studies did by Krishnamoorthy et al. at Coimbatore, Rajan SP et al. at Coimbatore and Vidyalakshmi et al. at, Thiruvallur, ([8]-[10]).

In our study significant association was found between malnutrition and gender, which was similar to other studies conducted by Krishnamoorthy et al. at Coimbatore, Rajan SP et al. at Coimbatore, Vidyalakshmi et al. at, Thiruvallur, Joymatiet al. at Manipur, Agarwalla et al. at Assam and Lahiri et al. at West Bengal ([8], [12],[14]). This could be attributed to traditionally existing cultural practice of prioritizing their family members over themselves. Among the study participants 43% were illiterate, there is no significant association between education and malnourishment in our study. There is no relationship between the educational status of the study participants and knowledge about intake of healthy foods. However, in contrast, studies conducted by Joymatiet al. at Manipur show strong association states that higher education has better nutritional awareness and healthy lifestyle which was contrary to our study [11].

Our study shows that 11% were malnourished and 52% were at risk of malnutrition by using Mini Nutritional Assessment (MNA) Questionnaire. Similar results for the prevalence of malnutrition was found in various studies conducted Vidyalakshmi et al. at, Thiruvallur (17.9%), Agarwalla et al. at Assam (15%) and Chataut et al. at nepal (11.6%) using MNA Questionnaire ([10],[12],[15]). Other studies have reported higher prevalence by Lahiri et al. at West Bengal (29.4%) due to geographical variation which covers a larger study area ([8]-[9],[16]). Prevalence of at risk of malnutrition was found to be 52%. Similar results were reported in studies by Krishnamoorthy et al. at Coimbatore (58.8%), Vidyalakshmi et al. at, Thiruvallur (48.8%), Joymatiet al. at Manipur (49.2%) and Agarwalla et al. at Assam (55%) ([8],[10]-[12]). Among the study participants majority (55.7%) of them were aged between 60 – 70 years and there was significant association between malnutrition and age of the study participants. Similar results were reported by Krishnamoorthy et al. at Coimbatore, Rajan SP et al. at Coimbatore, and Patil et al. at Karnataka ([8],[9],[16]). Advancing age has major impact on malnutrition among elderly population by Arafat et al. at Bangladesh [17]. The result in our study proves that physiological changes among elderly population affect food intake which may lead to loss of appetite attributing to nutritional deficiency.

Along with the factors contributing to malnutrition, social isolation plays a significant role, which emphasizes that social support was important in this age group. Elderly people need help to take care of themselves for their physical support and also to prevent from any risk of fall, injuries, or ignorance in future. To meet the nutritional requirements among elderly population, nutritional supplements with adequate vitamins, minerals, proteins and fortified foods can be used to attain a healthier lifestyle ([12],[15]). Timely recognition of malnourishment with nutrition support can prevent or reduce mortality and morbidity among elderly population. More research is required to evaluate the underlying cause of malnutrition for appropriate treatment. A

personalized multidimensional approach includes dietary modification, nutritional supplements, counselling and psychosocial support which can be given to the elderly for a health life ([7],[18]).

The limitation in our study was cause-effect relationship and generalisability to other areas could not be evaluated since it is cross-sectional. Detailed dietary chart for the study participants was also not included in the study.

CONCLUSION

The overall at risk of malnutrition was high, which is an alarming and unnoticed problem prevailing in our study area. Early intervention with a multi-dimensional approach is recommended for the elderly population for effective planning of interventions and policy-making. Further, need of more studies exclusively for diet intake is required at individual level to explore the actual cause-effect relationship. To prevent elderly malnutrition in the future, individual screening at the household level with psychosocial support is recommended.

REFERENCES

1. Ageing and health [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 5]. Available from: <https://www.who.int/news-room/fact-sheets/detail/ageing-and-health>
2. Shuremu M, Belachew T, Hassen K. Nutritional status and its associated factors among elderly people in Ilu Aba Bor Zone, Southwest Ethiopia: a community-based cross-sectional study. *BMJ Open*. 2023 Jan 31;13(1):e067787.
3. Kaur D, Rasane P, Singh J, Kaur S, Kumar V, Mahato DK, et al. Nutritional Interventions for Elderly and Considerations for the Development of Geriatric Foods. *Curr Aging Sci*. 2019;12(1):15–27.
4. Malik C, Khanna S, Jain Y, Jain R. Geriatric population in India: Demography, vulnerabilities, and healthcare challenges. *J Fam Med Prim Care*. 2021 Jan 19;10.
5. Mathew AC, Das D, Sampath S, Vijayakumar M, Ramakrishnan N, Ravishankar SL. Prevalence and correlates of malnutrition among elderly in an urban area in Coimbatore. *Indian J Public Health*. 2016;60(2):112–7.
6. Estimates of malnutrition and risk of malnutrition among the elderly (≥ 60 years) in India: A systematic review and meta-analysis - ScienceDirect [Internet]. [cited 2024 Jul 5]. Available from: <https://www.sciencedirect.com/science/article/abs/pii/S1568163720302725>
7. Norman K, Haß U, Pirlich M. Malnutrition in Older Adults—Recent Advances and Remaining Challenges. *Nutrients*. 2021 Aug 12;13(8):2764.

8. Krishnamoorthy Y, Vijayageetha M, Kumar SG, Rajaa S, Rehman T. Prevalence of malnutrition and its associated factors among elderly population in rural Puducherry using mini-nutritional assessment questionnaire. *J Fam Med Prim Care*. 2018;7(6):1429–33.
9. Rajan SP, Jeevithan S, Shanmugapriya D, Padmavathy L. Nutritional status assessment among elderly population in a rural area of South India. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2020 Jun 26;7(7):2760–3.
10. Vidyalakshmi M, Kirubhakaran B. Assessment of Nutritional Status and Its Associated Factors in Elderly in Rural Area of Tamil Nadu, India. *Galore Int J Health Sci Res*. 2021 May 18;6(1):38–43.
11. O J, Ningombam M, Rajkumari B, Gangmei A. Assessment of nutritional status among elderly population in a rural area in Manipur: community-based cross-sectional study. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2018 Jun 22;5(7):3125–9.
12. Agarwalla R, Saikia A, Barua R. Assessment of the nutritional status of the elderly and its correlates. *J Fam Community Med*. 2015 Feb 6;22:39–43.
13. Tomar R, Chhabra DP. Assessment of the Nutritional Health Status of Rural Old People in District Saharanpur (U.P.). 2018;(4).
14. Lahiri S, Biswas A, Santra S, Lahiri S. Assessment of nutritional status among elderly population in a rural area of West Bengal, India. 2015 Jan 1;1.
15. Chataut J, Jonche S, Ghimire M, Tamrakar D, Bhandari MS. Prevalence of Malnutrition among Elderly People Living in a Rural Area of Nepal. *JNMA J Nepal Med Assoc*. 2021 Feb;59(234):146–51.
16. Patil DJ, Shindhe MM. Nutritional status assessment of elderly using MNA tool in rural Belagavi: a cross sectional study. *Int J Community Med Public Health*. 2018 Oct 25;5(11):4799–803.
17. Razon AH, Haque MdI, Ahmed MdF, Ahmad T. Assessment of dietary habits, nutritional status and common health complications of older people living in rural areas of Bangladesh. *Heliyon*. 2022 Feb 11;8(2):e08947.
18. Vranešić Bender D, Krznarić Ž. Nutritional issues and considerations in the elderly: an update. *Croat Med J*. 2020 Apr;61(2):180–3.